

Optimization of physical parameter for the production of L-lysine by a mutant strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀

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Manuscript received 17 October 2011, accepted 22 February 2012

Abstract : The production of L-lysine shake flask fermentation of *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀, has been investigated through optimization of several parameters like pH, period of incubation, age of inoculums, volume of inoculums, volume of media and temperature were optimized individually one by one. Maximum production of L-lysine was obtained at pH 7.2; period of incubation 72 h; age of inoculums, 48 h; volume of inocula, 6 mL (7.2×10^7 cells/mL); volume of media, 25 mL and 30 °C. The production of L-lysine by a auxotrophic mutant AB₂₀₀ increased from 8.1 mg/mL to 10.9 mg/mL after this experimental study.

Keywords : *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀, physical parameters, auxotroph, L-lysine.

Introduction

With the tremendous utilization of lysine in animal fields its economic importance increases continuously as well. This focus the attention of over production of this essential amino acid¹. Better production of L-lysine were obtained by repeated mutation. In our laboratory we have already developed a high L-lysine yielding biotin requiring auxotrophic mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ from a regulatory mutant *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₅. However, other parameters such as nutritional and physical environment to which an organism is exposed are also known to significantly altered product yield². Regarding the industrial production of L-lysine, much effort were still going on to improve its production, especially from the viewpoint of its production cost. Many reviews are available on the effects of different physical parameters for the production of L-amino acids by using different microorganism³⁻⁵. To maximize the production, the effect of different physical parameters namely initial pH, period of incubation, volume of inoculums, age of inoculums and the temperature were examined one by one using the basal salt medium.

Materials and methods :

Microorganism :

Micrococcus glutamicus AB₂₀₀ developed by induced mutation (using UV rays as physical mutagen and methyl

methane sulfonate as chemical mutagen) in our laboratory was used throughout this study.

Basal salt medium for L-lysine production :

Basal salt medium contained glucose : 9%, Urea : 0.2%, K₂HPO₄ : 0.1%, MgSO₄.7H₂O : 0.020%, yeast extract : 0.2%, pH : 7.2.

Statistical analysis :

Data were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$. The data was analyzed by student's t test, by using MS Excel. Two measurements were considered significant if the corresponding p value < 0.05 and considered highly significant if $p < 0.01$.

Estimation of dry cell weight :

The cells were separated from the fermentation medium by filtration, washed with distilled water and filtered once again. The mass was dried in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h. It was then weighed to obtain the dry cell weight.

Analysis of amino acids :

Descending paper chromatography was employed for detecting L-lysine in culture medium and was run for 16 to 18 h on Watmann no. 1 chromatographic paper. Solvent system : n -butanol : acetic acid : water 2 : 1 : 1. The spots were visualized by spraying with a solution of 0.2% ninhydrine in acetone and quantitative estimation of L-lysine in the suspension was done using colorimetric estimation method.

Recovery and identification of L-lysine :

For the identification of L-lysine the fermentation broth after separation of cells was adjusted to pH 5 with HCl and filtered. The filtrate was then treated with active charcoal to remove the colored impurity. After filtration the clear filtrate was finally passed through a Dowex 50 (H⁺-type) column in which the amino acid was absorbed. After washing with water and elution with 0.24 (N) HCl, the elute was further passed through an Amberlite (H⁺-type) for elimination of chloride ion. The elute was concentrated by evaporation in vacuum and the product was obtained in a crystalline form in the cold. The pure material is proved to be L-lysine both by chemical test, optical rotation and by paper chromatographic method.

Insoluble picrate derivative of L-lysine was prepared and melting point of the derivative 266 °C⁴. Elemental analysis of the pure material gave the following values : C - 49.31%, H - 9.63%, N - 19.17%, O - 21.88%. Whereas the molecular calculation shows the following values : C - 49.29%, H - 9.65%, N - 9.16%, O - 21.89%. The optical rotation was estimated as : (L)_D²⁵ = 20.1 (C = 2, 5 N HCl).

These data agreed with those of lysine.

Results and discussion

Effect of initial pH :

Initially the pH of the production medium was adjusted using 0.1 (N) NaOH and 0.1 (N) HCl. The effect of pH on L-lysine production was examined among six different levels (5.5 to 8.0) of initial pH of the media. Production of L-lysine was maximum (8.1 mg/mL) at pH 7.2 (by *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Fig. 1)). With further increase in pH production decreases significantly.

Fig. 1. Effect of initial pH of the medium on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean ± SEM, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

Growth is usually sensitive to pH of the medium. The process of microbial growth changes the pH of the medium due to accumulation of different secondary metabolites⁵. Broer *et al.*⁶ found that optimum pH for maximum velocity of transport by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* was 7.4–7.6. Kelle *et al.*⁷ studied the L-lysine transport by *Corynebacterium glutamicum* found that pH value governed the transport activity and maximum L-lysine export rate was revealed at pH 7.0.

Effect of period of incubation :

To determine the optimum period of incubation for L-lysine production the culture media were incubated for different period ranging from 24 to 96 h and it was observed that at 72 h incubation the production of L-lysine was maximum (Fig. 2). With increase in time cell growth increases significantly along with production.

Fig. 2. Effect of period of incubation on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean ± SEM, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

Effect of age of inoculums :

To study the effect of age of inoculums six different ages (Ranging from 18 to 72 h) of inocula were studied to

Fig. 3. Effect of the age of inoculums on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean ± SEM, **p < 0.01, *p < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

yield maximum amount of L-lysine. Maximum efficiency to produce L-lysine was by the organism was observed at 48 h age. It is probably at the late lag phase and early lag phase of growth, the rate of L-amino acid accumulation is highest by bacteria^{8,9}. 24 h might be too early to reach at the late lag phase and more than 60 h is too late and the growth of the organism may go to the late lag phase or stationary phase.

Effect of volume of inoculums :

Six different volumes of inocula were studied to optimize the cell density. Maximum L-lysine yield was obtained at 6 mL (7.2×10^7 cells/ml) of inoculums size. Above and below 6 mL L-lysine accumulation was decreased gradually.

Fig. 4. Effect of volume of inoculums on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean \pm SEM, ***p* < 0.01, **p* < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

Too low a cell density may give insufficient biomass and too high density may produce too much biomass and deplete the substrate of nutrient necessary for L-lysine fermentation.

Fig. 5. Effect of volume of the medium on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean \pm SEM, ***p* < 0.01, **p* < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

Effect of volume of medium :

To optimize the volume of the media, six different volumes were examined. After 72 h of inoculation, it was observed that L-lysine production is highest for 25 mL medium contained in a 100 mL Erlenmeyer flask.

Too high media volume may dilute the acid content whereas too low a volume may give insufficient nutrient for the growth of the microorganism and production of desired metabolite declines sharply^{11,12}.

Effect of temperature :

The effect of a wide range of operational temperature on L-lysine fermentation was carried out in a shake flask.

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on L-lysine production by *M. glutamicus* AB₂₀₀ (Values expressed as mean \pm SEM, ***p* < 0.01, **p* < 0.05 compared to control). (□) Production (mg/mL) and (■) Cell growth (mg/mL).

At 30 °C maximum yield of L-lysine (10.9 mg/mL) as well as maximum biomass (3.98 mg/mL) was obtained by the experimental strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀.

Temperature also plays an important role on growth rate of microorganism. The shift in temperature can alter the utilization rate of one component as compared to other, thus unbalance the media with respect to growth. A wide range of optimum and operational temperature have been disclosed in the international patent bibliography for L-lysine fermentation¹¹. Hilliger *et al.*⁹ observed the influence of temperature was one of the major fermentation parameters on growth and L-lysine formation of *Corynebacterium glutamicum* and suggested that 29 °C is optimum temperature for both biomass and L-lysine yield^{13,14}.

Therefore, from our present experimental study, it was concluded that using minimum salt medium, by optimizing different physical parameters, production of L-lysine was increased from 8.1 mg/mL to 10.9 mg/mL by the mutant strain *Micrococcus glutamicus* AB₂₀₀.

Acknowledgement

We express our sincere thanks to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) for providing us the grant for this research work and to the Librarians of Bose Institute, Kolkata.

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